

Designing a Productive Workspace Optimisation - Maturity Model (PWO-MM)

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Abstract. The built environment has a measurable impact on the productivity of knowledge workers. There is, therefore, a growing need in the industry for information systems (IS) organisations to align their work environment with the needs of their workers, ensuring high productivity levels. To enable strategic improvements to their work environment, there is an opportunity for a tool that can be used to benchmark the current capabilities of an organisation to provide human-centred workspaces for increased productivity, which can also serve as a strategic roadmap to enable future improvements. To this end, a proposed maturity model was developed in multiple phases. Firstly, a structured literature review was conducted to understand the constituents of IS knowledge worker productivity, which informed the first collection of maturity model dimensions. Thereafter, a structured literature review and focus group was conducted to understand how productivity is managed and measured in IS workspaces. Based on these findings, core productivity dimensions were identified that can be used to gauge perceived productivity improvements over time. Lastly, another structured literature review and focus group was conducted to determine the strategic objectives for the development of a productive work environment, which were used to enrich the initial set of maturity model dimensions. Exemplary case mappings were then conducted on three unique cases using publicly available data, to instantiate the proposed Productive Workspace Optimisation - Maturity Model (PWO-MM). The model proved sensitive enough to map organisational capabilities of high, mid and low maturity organisations, demonstrating its utility in industry as a strategic tool for workplace management.

Keywords: Productivity, Information Systems Knowledge Workers, Work Environment, Workplace Management, Maturity Model.

1 Introduction

Fast-paced digitalisation has led to an upsurge in organisations implementing remote or hybrid work policies, rather than traditional in-office work policies [1]. Remote work; however, provides limited opportunities for collaboration, knowledge dissemination, and maintaining team cohesion and camaraderie [2]. For these reasons, many employers have shown a preference for having their workers return to work as part of a hybrid work model or full-time in the office [3]. Studies have shown that the built

environment has a significant impact on the productivity of its occupants [2, 4, 5]. Workspaces should, therefore, be designed to best serve the needs of workers, ensuring high levels of productivity [5].

Organisations that produce information systems (IS) face unique productivity challenges, as IS knowledge worker productivity differs from traditional input-output measures used in industries such as manufacturing [6]. It is often assessed through perceived productivity, which compares a worker's current productivity to their historical performance [7]. In this study, IS knowledge workers refer to professionals involved in the software development life cycle, including developers, testers, analysts, designers, and project managers.

The purpose of this study is to instantiate a maturity model that aims to guide organisations in assessing their current capabilities in providing a productive workspace and to serve as a roadmap for improving these capabilities. The research was guided by the research question "How can a maturity model be used to guide human-centred space design for productivity in IS work environments?" This paper is structured as follows: first, the background to the research is discussed, followed by the research methodology, the results and validation of the findings. The paper's discussion and contribution are then presented, followed by the paper's conclusion.

2 Background

Since the 1990's, there has been a growing awareness of the need to align workspace design with that of its workforce [8]. Although there has been significant research into how workspaces should be designed [9-11] there is a gap surrounding how workspace design should be undertaken from a strategic workspace management point of view.

Productivity, in most industries, is measured simply as input versus output [12]. It is, however, notoriously difficult to measure productivity within the IS work environment due to the complex factors that can influence IS knowledge worker productivity [13]. Team dynamics, resource availability, project phases and other socio-human factors all have an impact on the productivity levels of IS knowledge workers [4].

Knowledge worker productivity is significantly impacted by the design and layout of the work environment they inhabit [5]. Although workspace improvements are costly, the productivity gains often outweigh the benefits of reducing expenditure on workplace design and management [14]. Workplaces that fail to meet knowledge workers' needs reduce productivity by lowering job satisfaction and increasing absenteeism and disengagement [15]. It is therefore critical for organisations to include workplace management as part of their long-term strategic planning.

Maturity models are valuable strategic tools grounded in staged growth theory, providing organisations with a progressive roadmap for capability development [16]. Maturity models are also informed by capability theories, which emphasise coordinating resources to achieve strategic advantage [17].

They are further underpinned by process improvement theory, with models such as CMMI illustrating how structured practices lead to greater efficiency and control [12]. Maturity models also draw on organisational learning [18] and institutionalisation

theory [19], positioning higher maturity as a reflection of embedded organisational processes and knowledge. These foundations support their use for capability assessment and improvement planning.

At the time of writing, no maturity model addresses the capabilities required for productive workspace design. Existing models mainly focus on operational processes rather than workplace management [12]. To address this gap, this study proposes a maturity model for evaluating organisations' capabilities to support productive IS knowledge workspaces.

3 Methodology

The proposed maturity model was developed through various cycles of pragmatic research, involving the collection of both primary and secondary data. A combination of qualitative data collection methods was utilised, including structured literature reviews (SLR) and focus groups (FG).

3.1 Determining the maturity levels, dimensions and strategic objectives for the proposed maturity model

An SLR was conducted to identify the constituents of IS knowledge worker productivity and group them into organisational domains, forming the initial maturity model dimensions. These dimensions were refined through focus group discussions on using user-centred design to improve workspace productivity. Strategic objectives and activities for each maturity level were synthesised from the SLR and focus group data. Participants were selected through non-probability purposive sampling based on their knowledge of the phenomenon [12]. The following selection criteria were used to identify participants:

- The participant identifies as an IS knowledge worker
- The participant works from a physical office location regularly
- The participant's work objectives include creating IS artefacts or managing teams that produce IS artefacts

Following Smithson [20]'s recommendation of 6–12 participants, a two-hour in-person focus group was conducted with nine participants: three software developers, three designers, and three service delivery staff members. Participants used a digital whiteboard to collaboratively capture responses. To identify workspace elements that enhance productivity, the "love and breakup letter method" (LBM) was used to uncover participants' preferences, needs, and frustrations [21]. The following questions formed part of the FG protocol:

- Write a "love letter" and a "breakup letter" to your current work environment. In these letters, list all the things you currently like or dislike about your work environment, considering the impact on your productivity.

- How would you modify your current work environment to address the frustrating elements?
- How would you enhance the features of the work environment that you like?

3.2 Determining the core productivity dimensions

To evaluate the impact of workspace improvements on productivity, an SLR and focus group were conducted to identify how IS knowledge worker productivity is measured in academia and practice. The following criteria were used to identify participants:

- The participant must currently be working within the IS industry.
- The participant must be part of an organisation and not self-employed.
- The participant must work in a hybrid or in-person work environment.
- The participant's job role must include the creation of IS artefacts or the management of teams that produce IS artefacts.

FG participants were asked:

- In your role of creating software products, how do you define productivity?
- What do you consider to be a productive day?
- What do you feel causes you to have an unproductive day?
- How do you boost your productivity when you perceive yourself as unproductive?
- How do you measure productivity within your team?
- What challenges do you face in measuring productivity in your team?

The session was recorded for deeper analysis. The data from the session was then cleaned, sorted and thematically analysed through open coding.

3.3 Maturity model design

To instantiate the proposed maturity model, case mapping was conducted using three IS organisations with sufficient publicly available data on workspace design and productivity. Case mapping aligns theoretical concepts with empirical evidence to validate a model's practical applicability [22, 23]. The proposed maturity model (PWO-MM), illustrated in Fig. 1, integrates these aspects into a single framework, discussed further in the following section.

3.4 Levels, dimensions and strategic objectives for PWO-MM

Maturity models describe progressive levels of capability. In this study, the capability refers to an organisation's ability to provide workspaces that enhance productivity. The model was developed using a top-down approach, defining levels before the measures required to achieve them [24]. PWO-MM consists of five levels representing increasing managerial capability and workforce involvement in workspace design: (1) Unstructured, (2) Foundational Awareness, (3) Managed, (4) Maintained and Sustainable, and (5) People-Driven and Optimised.

Maturity model dimensions enable a more holistic evaluation of complex domains and help organisations identify strengths and weaknesses to improve capability development and resource allocation [24]. An SLR was conducted to identify the core workspace dimensions that support IS knowledge worker productivity. The initial dimensions included the physical environment, spatial configuration, organisational support, and occupant involvement in the design process.

A second SLR identified physical, cognitive, social, and affective workplace factors that influence productivity, including accessibility, ergonomics, adaptability, privacy, collaboration, safety, and environmental control. These findings informed a focus group protocol to elicit workspace needs affecting productivity. The resulting strategic objectives and activities refined the maturity model dimensions to accessibility, atmosphere, office layout, activity-based workspaces, and organisational culture. Organisational maturity increases as these strategic objectives are achieved.

3.5 Core Productivity Dimensions

PWO-MM aims to improve knowledge worker productivity, although no standard method exists for measuring IS knowledge worker productivity [2, 4]. This study used a focus group to identify productivity dimensions suitable for perceived productivity assessments. Eight dimensions were identified, including work quality, value creation, goal achievement, task progress, focus time, collaboration, role expectations, and workers' sense of accomplishment.

3.6 Model instantiation

Following Yin [25], this study used a multiple-case approach to instantiate the proposed maturity model using three organisations. The model was applied to identify organisational maturity, gaps, and improvement opportunities. Google and South Africa's Department of Public Service & Administration were selected through convenience sampling due to the availability of public data. The organisations were evaluated against the model dimensions to determine their capability to provide productive, human-centred work environments. Findings were then presented textually and visually.

The proposed Productive Workspace Optimisation – Maturity Model (PWO-MM) is illustrated in Fig. 1. The aim of the PWO-MM is to guide organisations in enhancing their capabilities to provide human-centred workspaces, designed around the needs of their knowledge workers, thereby enabling them to increase the productivity of their workforce. The PWO-MM can be used by managers of IS organisations to evaluate their current capabilities in providing productive IS workspaces and create a strategic workplace management plan to increase these capabilities to achieve higher levels of maturity.

Fig. 1. Productive Workspace Optimisation - Maturity Model

The following section outlines the three cases used to instantiate the PWO-MM. While the selected cases may not fully generalise to smaller IS organisations, many workplace design principles and implications of applying the model remain transferable [26, 27].

3.7 Case Mapping

Google

Google workspaces are designed to be flexible and adaptable, supporting collaboration, focus work, socialisation, and learning [28]. Their offices include meeting rooms, sprint spaces, lounges, and nature-connected areas, with team layouts structured to enhance collaboration [28]. Workspace design decisions are informed by observations, surveys, and interviews with employees [29, 30]. These improvements have contributed to increased productivity, employee fulfilment, and retention [29].

Monkey and River

This case mapping is based on observations from the researcher’s workplace, Monkey and River. The office provides workspaces, relaxation areas, and kitchen facilities, but has some accessibility and environmental comfort limitations. Meeting spaces are available but limited. At the time of writing, the organisation was relocating to a larger office with improved security, HVAC systems, and activity-based spaces designed to support focused work, meetings, and collaboration.

Department of Public Service & Administration.

South Africa's Department of Public Service & Administration (DPSA) is responsible for improving public service delivery, governance, and administrative efficiency [31]. However, the department faces challenges including skill shortages, toxic workplace culture, budget constraints, and delayed infrastructure maintenance [32, 33]. Reports describe the DPSA headquarters as unsafe and poorly maintained, with significant environmental and operational issues [33]. The department also struggles with fragmented systems and slow digital transformation, resulting in inefficiencies and reduced service delivery [34].

4 Results and Validation

Workspace management for the optimised productivity of knowledge workers requires strategic and long-term investment in organisational infrastructure and refinement of processes [14]. Organisations build on their capabilities and improve in predictable stages [35]. The levels and dimensions of these stages need to be defined, along with the strategic actions required to move between the dimensions, to guide the improvement of organisational capabilities and provide their workforce with workspaces optimised for productivity. Core productivity dimensions of IS knowledge workers must also be defined so that organisations can evaluate the impact that each stage of improvement has had on the productivity of their workforce.

4.1 Model validation

In the following section, the three case businesses are used to instantiate the PWO-MM model to determine the model's utility in practice and identify possible improvements to enhance its usefulness. First, the Google business case will be mapped, then the Monkey and River case study, followed by the DSPA case.

Google demonstrates a high level of maturity in its ability to provide workspaces that boost productivity, as shown in Table 1. In terms of accessibility, the workspace appears to align with the needs of all stakeholders and focuses on continual improvement [29, 30], achieving a maturity level of between four and five. For the dimension of atmosphere, Google's work environments are designed to create healthy, human-centred workplaces, with adequate lighting, air quality, thermal comfort, and noise control through acoustic design considerations [30, 36]. This demonstrates a high level of maturity in this capability, scoring between level four and five. In terms of office layout, Google displays level five maturity, since its workspaces are designed for maximum flexibility, featuring modular walls and furniture that can be adapted by teams to accommodate their specific needs [30]. It also reaches level five maturity for the activity-based workspaces dimension, since its work environments are designed based on years of observations and data collection to ensure an optimised environment that matches user needs [29, 30]. Lastly, Google displays a maturity level between four and five in organisational culture, as it strongly incorporates its culture into the design of its work environments and makes people-centred strategic decisions on workplace policies [29, 30].

Table 1. Google exemplary case mapping as an instantiation of PWO-MM

PWO-MM Dimension	Characteristic	Maturity Level
Accessibility	Aligned with the needs of all stakeholders, focussed on continual improvement	4-5
Atmosphere	Workspace atmosphere is maintained by regulatory quality and standards and continuously improved	4-5
Office layout	Flexible and driven by the needs of office occupants	5
Activity-based workspaces	Dependable activity-based workspaces, driven by the needs of the workers	5
Organisational culture	Data-driven changes to organisational culture to increase people-centredness	4-5

Monkey and river, as shown in Table 2, demonstrated an overall mid-range level of maturity. In terms of accessibility, although the workspace is not optimised for accessibility, the organisation is aware of its shortcomings and is actively working on improvements, giving it a score of level two. In terms of atmosphere, the current office space allows employees the freedom to manage characteristics of their work environment such as the temperature, but this can sometimes lead to the discomfort of others if all employees can not agree on a temperature. In the new office, a globally managed HVAC system will be in place, allowing the atmosphere to be regulated. This gives Monkey and River a maturity score of between level two and three. From both office layout and activity-based workspaces, the company is working in conjunction with an architect and space planner to develop optimised layouts for their new office, giving both of these a score of between level two and three. In terms of organisational culture, the organisation continuously ensures that its behaviour and policies align with its core value of being human-centred. These changes are currently not driven by data thus giving the organisation a score of level three.

Table 2. Monkey and River case mapping as an instantiation of PWO-MM

PWO-MM Dimension	Characteristic	Maturity Level
Accessibility	Initial consideration for accessibility	2
Atmosphere	Initial management of atmosphere	2-3
Office layout	Purposeful office layout	2-3
Activity-based workspaces	Initial implementation of activity-based design	2-3
Organisational culture	Discernibly People-centred	3

The DPSA, as shown in Table 3, displays a generally low maturity in its ability to provide a productive work environment for its staff. Badly maintained facilities with broken toilets, leaking ceilings, flooded corridors, broken ventilation, black dust particles and failing light fixtures [33, 36] indicate a low maturity in both accessibility and atmosphere dimensions, each gaining a rating of level one. There is no specific mention of office layout in the available resources; however, given the weak governance mentioned by Ali [37] and de Villiers [34], there is likely a lack of awareness of the impact

that the layout of an office has on the productivity of their workers, leading to a rating between level one and two. Similarly, for activity-based workspaces, scarcity of resources and failures in digitalisation lead to a low rating of between level one and two. Lastly, the indications of a toxic workplace culture and the blatant disregard for the safety of its workers suggest a lack of a people-centred culture [33, 38, 39].

Table 3. DPSA exemplary case mapping as an instantiation of PWO-MM

PWO-MM Dimension	Characteristic	Maturity Level
Accessibility	Low consideration for accessibility	1
Atmosphere	Poor management of atmosphere	1
Office layout	Lack of intent in office layout	1-2
Activity-based workspaces	Lack of activity-based workspaces	1-2
Organisational culture	Lack of people-centred culture	Level 1

5 Discussion and contribution

The purpose of this study was to propose a maturity model that can be used to guide organisations in assessing their current capabilities in providing a productive workspace and to serve as a roadmap for improving these capabilities. The maturity model was developed in multiple stages which included a combination of SLR's and FGs. From the findings the PWO-MM (Fig. 1) was proposed. The model was then mapped against exemplary real-world cases, namely Google, Monkey and River and DPSA, to evaluate the model's effectiveness and utility. The model proved sensitive enough to map the organisational capabilities of both high medium and low maturity organisations, demonstrating its utility in the industry as a strategic tool for workplace management.

This study contributed to the existing body of knowledge by proposing a maturity model that can be evaluate existing capabilities in providing productive workspaces. The study also contributes to the industry by providing a model that can guide strategic decision-making to improve organisational capabilities through strategic objectives and activities.

The researcher acknowledges the use of publicly available data and unsystematic observations of the researcher's place of work as limitations, as publicly available data may naturally present a positive picture of the organisations, and the researcher's familiarity with an organisation could introduce bias. Future research may include conducting more extensive case study analysis using primary data. Longitudinal studies may also be conducted on the effectiveness of PWO-MM as a tool to guide long term strategic workplace management.

6 Conclusion

This study proposed the PWO-MM, a maturity model aimed at measuring an organisation's capabilities to provide workspace accessibility, an atmosphere that is conducive

to work and ensure the well-being of the office occupants, a structured and strategic office layout, the availability of activity-based workspaces and a people-centred organisational culture. This model can be used by organisations as a strategic tool for evaluating their current capabilities in providing productive work environments, as well as serve as a road mapping tool to guide future improvements. The exemplary case study instantiation of the PWO-MM highlighted the applicability, utility and effectiveness of the model in determining organisational maturity. Although the outcome indicated the model's usefulness, primary case study and longitudinal studies on a wide range of organisations is suggested for future research to ensure the generalisation of the model.

7 Disclaimer

The author(s) declared no potential conflict of interest. Grammarly was used as a punctuation and spelling tool and was not used to generate content.

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